

Corrigenda and Addenda

Correction: Ethical Issues in Social Media Recruitment for Clinical Studies: Ethical Analysis and Framework

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In “Ethical Issues in Social Media Recruitment for Clinical Studies: Ethical Analysis and Framework” (JMIR 2022;24(5):e31231) the authors made one addition to the Acknowledgments section.

The funding note was missing in the originally published article. Therefore, the corrected version of the Acknowledgements’ section reads as follows:

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The correction will appear in the online version of the paper on the JMIR Publications website on September 7, 2022, together with the publication of this correction notice. Because this was made after submission to PubMed, PubMed Central, and other full-text repositories, the corrected article has also been resubmitted to those repositories.

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